

RSECon24 R Hackathon

Newcastle, 2024

Welcome!

- **Anyone** with an interest in contributing to R / open source contribution!
- Some potential tasks include:
 - Translating message strings to non-English languages
 - Reviewing the design of a dashboard, improving R help files
 - Testing patches in R/C code
 - Debugging GUI behaviour, etc.

Hackathon co-ordinators

- Heather Turner
- Saranjeet Kaur Bhogal
- Nick Tierney
- Ella Kaye (Online)

Plan

2 Sessions:

- Session 1: 11:00 - 12:30
- Session 2: 14:00 - 15:15

Communication

- Via slack channel “hackathon-r-development”

Tasks

- Hackathon tasks have been prepared as issues at: github.com/r-devel/r-dev-day/issues with label “RSECon24”.
- Welcome to add issues or discuss ideas for issues!
- See [spreadsheet](#) at QR code to express interest in issues

Working with remote participants

- Each group will have a Zoom breakout session they can use to text/video chat with people in their group
- Bringing headphones/earbuds would help so you can talk with less disruption/noise to remote participants
- You may also use the R Dev Container with Live Share so that you can collaborate on code and have a space to text chat on the same platform. This does not require you to learn how to build R, the release version of R is already available in the R Dev Container.

Key Links

- github.com/r-devel/r-dev-day
 - >> participant_resource_list.md